

LIBRARY USAGE ANALYSIS

Biswajit Paul

Library Information Assistant
Central Library, CIT Kokrajhar

Introduction: I am Biswajit Paul, a Library Information Assistant and an LIS professional presenting an analysis paper on Library Usage for One (01) Year (01st February 2023 to 31st January 2024). I am confident that this paper will be the first-ever analysis paper that is going to be published publicly.

Central Library, CIT Kokrajhar is a technically developed Library where 70% of the functions are involved technically with the help of WEB 3.0, SOUL 2.0, and RFID technology. Every transaction of the system is recorded digitally. Therefore, analysing of a periodic usage report shows the real outcome of the development.

Below, a working module of the sections and analysis are discussed. I believe that this analysis study will show you the real usage of the library.

Which technology/platform is used in which function of the library?

<i>Library Functions</i>	RFID	SOUL 2.0	SOCIAL MEDIA	WEBSITE	GOVT PROJE CTS	SELF REPOSI TORY	SUBSCRIBED PLATFORM	3 rd PART Y APPS
<i>Budget</i>		✓						✓
<i>Acquisition</i>		✓						✓
<i>Circulation</i>	✓	✓						
<i>Cataloguing</i>		✓		✓				
<i>Attendance</i>	✓							
<i>Membership</i>	✓	✓		✓				
<i>Repository Management</i>	✓	✓		✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
<i>Communication</i>			✓	✓				✓
<i>*CAS</i>			✓	✓				

Data Store	✓	✓		✓	✓	✓		
Fee/Transactions		✓		✓				
Printing Service								✓
Plagiarism				✓	✓		✓	✓
Security	✓	✓		✓		✓		✓

*CAS: Customer Awareness Programme.

Library System Architecture

Let us see the architecture diagram which describes the connections among the different systems of the library. All the modules define their different role and play different roles to fulfil the main objectives of the library.

Analysis and findings:

Different Platforms, Functions and Usage Statistics:

- RFID & SOUL 2.0**
 SOUL 2.0 implemented by INFLIBNET is a Library Management System (LMS) tool that provides a number of solutions for a Library like Budget, Acquisition, Cataloguing, Opac, Membership, Repository Management, and Circulation. SOUL 2.0 was installed

in the year of 2013. To be said SOUL 2.0 is the main heart of the library which stores and accumulates data on its database.

RFID is a technology used in Library Systems to track and monitor print resources like books, magazines, theses, reports, etc. RFID helps in easy asset tracking of the books, easy issue-return, and easy monitoring of the books. Due to use of the RFID, books cannot be easily lost, are Not required to stand in a queue for circulation, and Easy smart card system. It has several benefits in library systems.

Central Library also installed a Flap barrier gate to track daily usage of the library. Every user is issued a RFID-enabled smart card. This card helps us to get entry-exit in the library. Generally, this attendance system is handy for a library to get the real users of the library.

**** During analysis, date considered as 01st February 2023 to 31st January 2024 (One Year)**

Top 3 users

	Barnil Das 202202031031, BTech, ECE Total entry: 309
	Antaripa Das 202002012073, BTech, CE Total entry: 287
	Rinima Kalita 202002012074, BTech, CE Total entry: 279

- **Library portal and Repository Management System**

A library portal is a customized portal of a complete package of multiple functions starting from dynamic websites to day-to-day activity database management systems. The library provides the following functionalities:

The analysis of the portal is done with the help of a Google console report. Due to security reasons, the financial part is not included in this analysis.

Total site view:

Top 6 queries to search CIT Kokrajhar library

- cit library
- cit previous year question paper
- cit kokrajhar previous year question paper
- laser security system project report pdf
- citk library
- cit kokrajhar library

Top 10 page search

- <http://centrallibrary.cit.ac.in/QuestionPaper>
- ANALYSIS AND DESIGN OF R.C.C. OVERHEAD TANK
- <http://centrallibrary.cit.ac.in/>
- Smart Traffic Management System using Internet of Things (IoT)
- Automatic Water Level Controller using 555 Timer
- Laser Security System
- Automatic Door Opening Closing System using PIR Sensor
- Smart street light system
- Touchless door bell
- HEARTBEAT SENSOR USING ARDUINO

Top 10 countries search library website

Repository download

- **Usage of Plagiarism Software**

Total users: 123

Software using: Turnitin.

The duration during the analysis of the report: 01/02/2023 to 31/01/2024

Monthwise submitted documents for plagiarism

Top 5 users from faculty

Top 5 users from Scholar

Besides these, Central Library is using social media platforms for customer awareness services through different social media as given in figure.

Conclusion: Through the analysis, I have worked with 3 different databases with a volume of more than 20-130 GB each, and records of the last 10 years. After analysing the usage statistics, it is clear that the facilities of the central library are generating a great positive outcome. Also, it would not be my mistake if I mentioned that the library can be considered as one of the best libraries in Assam from the perspective of its infrastructure, facilities, digitization, resources, and the activeness of the working staff. There are very few libraries that can be able to generate such a huge level of outcome statistics.

“At last, I would like to convey my heartiest thanks to all readers for sparing your valuable time.”